

Characterization

Participant ID	Experience time	Previous contact with MFE	Previous contact description	Group
P1	-	No	-	A
P2	-	No	-	B
P3	-	No	-	B
P4	Between 1 and 2 years	No	-	B
P5	-	No	-	B
P6	Between 1 and 2 years	No	-	B
P7	-	No	-	A
P8	-	No	-	A
P9	-	No	-	A
P10	-	No	-	B
P11	-	No	-	A
P12	Less than 1 year	No	-	A
P13	-	No	-	B
P14	-	No	-	B
P15	-	No	-	A
P16	-	No	-	B
P17	-	No	-	B
P18	-	No	-	B
P19	-	No	-	A
P20	-	No	-	A
P21	-	No	-	A
P22	-	No	-	A
P23	Between 2 and 3 years	No	-	A